

PEDAGOGICAL METHODS OF SPORTS SELECTION IN BOXING

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Annotation: The article examines the problems of selection of young boxers and suggests ways of pedagogical solutions to the problems of sports selection in boxing.

Key words: sports selection, psychodiagnostic information, boxing, recruitment of national teams, pedagogical tasks, motivational complex.

Introduction. To successfully solve the problems of physical training and sports training in boxing, training and education of young athletes, knowledge of their individual characteristics is necessary [2, 4, 5]. Obtaining appropriate psychodiagnostic information opens up certain pedagogical opportunities for selecting capable athletes in boxing and recruiting a sports team. In sports practice, there are three main areas of scientifically based psychodiagnostic methods for pedagogical purposes:

1. Finding out which sport is appropriate for a beginner to engage in [1].
2. Formation of a sports team from capable athletes who perform at sports competitions as a single unit [3].
3. Selection of psychologically stable, highly motivated athletes with an equally high level of qualifications and tactical and technical training [6, 7].

The selection problem is closely related to the solution of five pedagogical problems:

1. Determination of model characteristics of the “ideal athlete” - construction of a sports program with pedagogically sound requirements for the psychological composition, personality and moral-volitional qualities of the athlete.
2. Forecasting an athlete’s success in training and competitions of various scales.
3. Increasing the efficiency of selection, which is directly related to methods for predicting the psychodiagnostics of an athlete’s personality.
4. Improving the organization of educational and training activities of athletes, clarifying its features success and advancement in the educational process.
5. Increasing the effectiveness of the athlete’s actions in a further real situation with all possible complicated situations, including extreme conditions of training loads and competitions [8, 10, 11].

At the first stage, solving problems of sports orientation is based on model characteristics of the psychological characteristics of athletes, compiled in accordance with the requirements of a sports program for a given sport. The pedagogical difficulty lies in correctly identifying certain abilities and important sports qualities of an athlete necessary for him to successfully perform requirements of the coach and conditions of competitive activity. At the second stage, the solution of pedagogical problems of sports training is based on in-depth model characteristics and psychological characteristics of athletes [9,12, 13].

At the third stage, solving the problems of selecting the most reliable athletes for the team is based on the individual predictive psychological and pedagogical characteristics of a particular boxer, implemented under extreme conditions of competition [7, 14].

Psychodiagnostic materials provide great assistance to the coach in organizing training sessions and scientifically providing an individual approach to the education of a boxer.

Knowledge of the individual characteristics of athletes allows the coach to methodically manage the educational and training process. The basis of sport is made up of three elements: selection, training, competition.

The need for selection is due to the fact that:

- the period of active sports life of a boxer is short (on average 5-10 years);
- individual mental characteristics (mental functions, psychomotor skills, personality traits) do not allow everyone to achieve high sports results within an acceptable time frame. For example, out of 10,000 children who start playing sports, only 3 achieve master results international class sports [15].

The purpose of selection is to identify athletes whose training process would give maximum effect with minimal time investment.

According to experts, the main methodological principles are as follows:

1. Systematicity, which requires the joint development of a selection procedure, studying the mental characteristics of high-class athletes, predicting training results and sports achievements.
2. Scientific validity, methods and selection criteria, which allows you to avoid serious mistakes.
3. Selection in sports, the problem is multifaceted: social, pedagogical, medical, economic, psychological. A decision on the fate of an athlete can only be made on the basis of the entire complex of information.
4. Prolonged dynamic selection. Selection in sports should be a continuous process of studying and diagnosing mental properties and personality traits that are important for sports activities. Such studies are carried out regularly throughout sports life at different stages of sports improvement.
5. Pedagogical value. The results of a psychodiagnostic examination of athletes should be used not only to select the most gifted athletes, but also to manage the training process, improve conditions for competitions: purposeful construction of education and training processes, rationalization of training programs, regulation of loads, improvement of educational and training tools.
6. Adaptability of selection criteria. The criteria for deciding an athlete's fitness must be flexible and changing. The need to increase or decrease them periodically

arises in connection with changes in requirements for athletes due to an increase or decrease in sports competition in the country and in the international arena.

7. Humanism. Selection should protect the athlete from stresses and disappointments that are unbearable for his psyche, associated with the wrong choice of a sport or sport specializations.

8. Relevance. The development of a system of psychological selection is necessary and appropriate, because competitive Athletes' achievements depend significantly not only on their abilities, but also on individual mental qualities.

9. Practical usefulness. Activities for psychological selection must be cost-effective in terms of material costs for equipment and training, justified in the frequency and duration of examinations and prompt (timely issuance of a psychodiagnostic report) [5].

The psychological selection system includes four stages.

1. Formation of target features.

The success of sports activities can decide the fate of an athlete when selected as a target trait. Target characteristics determine the meaning and reasonableness of selection tasks.

Experience in this area indicates that it is much more promising to use objectively and unambiguously recorded results (seconds, points, meters, kilometers or occupied place) as target characteristics. Expert coaching or referee assessments of athletes' qualifications can also be used as target characteristics. When collecting such information, requirements should be followed to ensure its reliability.

2. Selection of prognostic signs.

Prognostic features include those that are used to predict future values of target features. In sports psychodiagnostics, this quality is represented by the results of a psychodiagnostic examination of athletes. They should be used to predict sports qualifications, level of achievement, competitive stability and other target characteristics of an athlete.

3. Construction of a selection model. The success of sports activities cannot be reliably predicted by just one prognostic sign.

Achieving high results in any sport depends simultaneously on many psychological characteristics of the athlete. They are distinguished by a certain independence and are often specially selected to show the versatile nature of the demands of sports activity in relation to the mental qualities of the athlete.

Conclusions. 1. Sports selection in boxing is a key pedagogical task that ensures the success of an athlete's training.

2. Psychophysiological and technical-tactical indicators alone are not enough for the successful selection of athletes.

When selecting for a national team, it is necessary to take into account the motivational complex of candidates.

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